

Studies on the Claisen Rearrangement in $\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethylallyloxycoumarins

B. Chaudhury, S. K. Saha, and (Mrs.) A. Chatterjee

Claisen migration of $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethyl allyl ethers of 5-hydroxy-, 6-hydroxy-, 7-hydroxy-, and 8-hydroxy-coumarins has been studied. These $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethylallyloxycoumarins do not undergo any molecular rearrangement but suffer degradation to phenolic coumarins and isoprene under the experimental conditions at which Claisen rearrangement is performed. A plausible mechanism for this degradation and abnormal reaction has been discussed.

Claisen rearrangement has been extensively investigated and has gained a great importance in synthetic chemistry, in stereospecific introduction of angular substituents, and in the determination of bond structures in aromatic compounds¹. The nature of the reaction, of the intermediate produced during the course of the rearrangement and, the reaction mechanism have been studied by various workers² and a definite assessment on these particular aspects could be made with the help of isotopic tracer technique.

Claisen rearrangement has been shown to be the kinetically first order, unimolecular reaction involving the inversion of the allyl side chain. The intermediates during the migration have been characterised as dienones¹⁻⁴ and the rearrangement has been shown to involve a cyclic mechanism^{1,3}.

Further investigation by Alexander and Kluber⁵ has demonstrated that the Claisen migration is stereospecific and the geometry in the allyl group has a pronounced effect on the rate of the rearrangement which has been examined by Huestis and Andrews⁶ as also by White and Norcross⁷. The latter have proved that the transition state of the Claisen rearrangement must have the atoms of the allyl group, the ether oxygen, and the 1- and 2-carbons of the aromatic ring in a distorted chair conformation. Thus extensive studies on the Claisen migration of allyl ethers and γ -methyl allyl ethers have been made and are still being continued, but very little is known about the rearrangement

1. D. S. Tarbell, "The Claisen Rearrangement" in R. Adams' "Organic Reactions", Vol. II, Published by John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York, 1945, pp. 1-48; M. S. Newman, "Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry", John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York, 1956, pp. 295-303; E. S. Gould, "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry", E. S. Holt & Co., Inc., New York, 1959, pp. 644-649.
2. Fahrni and Schmid, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1959, **42**, 1102.
3. Haegge and Schmid, *ibid.*, 1958, **41**, 657.
4. Conroy and Firestone, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 2290.
5. *Ibid.*, 1951, **73**, 4304.
6. *Ibid.*, 1961, **83**, 1963.
7. *Ibid.*, 1961, **83**, 1968, 3265.

results obtained so far are summarised in Table I. All phenolic coumarins used in these reactions were prepared by standard methods and subsequently converted into the respective $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethyl allyl ethers by the action of $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethyl allyl bromide in acetone in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate.

From an examination of the degradation products, shown in Table I, it is observed that $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethylallyl moiety is being eliminated from the ethers as isoprene, which should participate readily in the Diels-Alder addition with maleic anhydride. Formation of this isoprene may be explained according to the following mechanism:

This view was subsequently confirmed as evidenced from the reactions discussed in the sequel.

$\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethyl allyl ethers of hydroxycoumarins (Table I) were heated in a sealed tube in dry xylene in presence of maleic anhydride. From the reaction products, the maleic anhydride adduct of isoprene could be isolated besides the expected phenolic coumarins.

TABLE I

$\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethyl allyl ether of coumarin.	UV spectra (λ_{max}).	I.R. spectra (peaks at).	Characteristics.	Results of experiments carried out under different conditions.	
				Heated in (i) benzene (ii) xylene.	Pyrolysis products.
1. 5-Hydroxy- (m.p. 62-64°)	259m μ (log ϵ , 4.05)	5.75 μ	$\alpha\beta$ -Unsaturated- δ -lactone.	(i) Complete elimination of allyl chain took place re-generating 5-hydroxycoumarin and producing isoprene. (ii) Same as above.	At 165-75°. (a) 5-Hydroxycoumarin (b) Isoprene.
	286 m μ (log ϵ , 4.09)	6.20	Phenyl nucleus or-C=C-		
		8.22	Phenyl ether		
2. 6-Hydroxy- (m.p. 126-27°)	228 m μ (log ϵ , 4.46)	5.83	$\alpha\beta$ -Unsaturated δ -lactone.	(i) The substance was recovered unchanged. (ii) Do	(i) At 170-80°, unchanged substance was recovered. (ii) At 200-210°. (a) 6-Hydroxy coumarin and (b) Isoprene.
	278 m μ (log ϵ , 4.12)	6.35	Phenyl nucleus or-C=C-		
	343 m μ (log ϵ , 3.05)	7.93	Phenyl ether		
3. 7-Hydroxy- (m.p. 77-78°)	323m μ (log ϵ , 4.200)	5.83	$\alpha\beta$ -Unsaturated δ -lactone	(i) Unchanged material was recovered. (ii) 5% was converted into umbelliferone, the rest remaining unchanged + a little isoprene.	(i) When heated at 167-70°/20 mm the substance was recovered unchanged. (ii) When heated at 175-85°/20 mm, complete elimination of allyl chain took place. (a) 7-Hydroxy coumarin was reformed with (b) liberation of isoprene. (iii) When heated at 175-85°/0.1 mm, the observation is the same as in (ii).
		6.13	Phenyl nucleus or-C=C-		
		8.03	Phenyl ether		
4. 8-Hydroxy- (m.p. 74-75°)	254 m μ (log ϵ , 4.04)	5.70	$\alpha\beta$ -Unsaturated- δ -lactone	(i) The substance was recovered unchanged. (ii) 50% of the substance underwent cleavage yielding 8-hydroxycoumarin + isoprene.	(i) At 170-80°. (a) 8-Hydroxy coumarin was regenerated along with (b) isoprene.
		6.19	Phenyl nucleus or-C=C-		
		8.13	Phenyl ether		

This obviously confirms the above view and the mechanism of the degradation of $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethyl allyl ethers of coumarins postulated above. An examination of the molecular models of these compounds showed that the elimination of $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethylallyl group as an isoprene moiety instead of its migration in neighbouring position was accentuated by the steric hindrance due to bulky methyl group in γ -C-atom. It was further revealed that one of the hydrogens of bulky methyl groups associated with the γ -carbon atom became firmly attached to the ether oxygen with the formation of a quasi six-membered ring. It seems that during this cyclic transition state, the ether oxygen pulls the hydrogen strongly enough to give rise to phenols by the rupture of the C-H bond (cf. hyper-conjugation) as shown above with the elimination of isoprene. This view, however, is yet to be confirmed and further work in this line is under way.

Anet *et al.*¹² prepared brayleanin from the sodium salt of scopoletin and $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethyl allyl bromide by a reaction involving a Claisen migration, but according to the observation of the present authors, it is hard to explain how this migration proceeds in 7- $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethyl allyl ether of scopoletin. Further studies on the mechanism of isoprene formation from $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethylallyloxycoumarins are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

$\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethyl Allyl Ether of 5-Hydroxycoumarin.—A solution of the coumarin (1g.) and $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethyl allyl bromide (2 g.) in dry acetone (30 ml) was refluxed for 20 hrs. on a water bath in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate. It was filtered, the residue thoroughly washed with hot acetone, the filtrate concentrated to a small bulk (5 ml), and poured into ice water with stirring when a solid separated. It was purified from unchanged phenolic coumarin by washing with 5% aqueous NaOH solution. It crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in fine white needles, m.p. 62-64°, yield 80%. (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ for 8 hrs.: C, 72.62; H, 6.25. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₄O₃: C, 73.04; H, 6.08%).

$\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethyl allyl ethers of 6-hydroxy-, 7-hydroxy-, and 8-hydroxy-coumarins were prepared according to the procedure described above.

$\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethyl Allyl Ether of 6-Hydroxycoumarin.—The compound crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in fine colorless granules, m.p. 126-27°, yield 80%. (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ for 8 hrs.: C, 72.7; H, 6.1. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₄O₃: C, 73.04; H, 6.08%).

$\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethyl Allyl Ether of 7-Hydroxycoumarin.—The product crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in shining flakes, m.p. 77-78°, yield 82%. (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ for 8 hrs.: C, 72.90; H, 6.18. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₄O₃: C, 73.04; H, 6.08%).

$\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethyl Allyl Ether of 8-Hydroxycoumarin.—The product on repeated crystallisation from petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°) melted at 74-75°, yield 78%. (Found in a

sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 8 hrs.: C, 73.22; H, 6.34. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{14}O_3$: C, 73.04; H, 6.08%.

Thermal Decomposition of $\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethyl Allyl Ethers of Hydroxycoumarins during Claisen Migration

1. *5-Hydroxycoumarin*.—(i). The allyl ether (0.2 g.) was dissolved in benzene and refluxed on a water bath for 10 hrs. The solvent was removed and the solid left was washed with 5% NaOH solution (aqueous), when all the solid dissolved completely. The aqueous solution was acidified and the solid precipitated was crystallised from benzene several times when fine white needles, m.p. 222-24°, were obtained. It did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample of 5-hydroxycoumarin (yield 80% of the theoretical). (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 8 hrs.: C, 66.62; H, 3.83. Calc. for $C_9H_6O_3$: C, 66.67; H, 3.70%). Pyrolysis experiment was performed and the products were worked up as shown below (Expt. 4, iii and iv).

2. *6-Hydroxycoumarin*.—(i). The allyl ether (0.2 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 170-80° for 2 hrs. The mass left was found to be insoluble in aqueous alkali and it crystallised from petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°) in fine granules, m.p. 126-27°. It did not depress the m.p. of the original substance. (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 8 hrs.: C, 66.40; H, 3.78. Calc. for $C_9H_6O_3$: C, 66.67; H, 3.70%).

3. *8-Hydroxycoumarin*.—(i). The allyl ether (0.28 g.) was heated at 170-80° in an oil bath for 2 hrs. An extremely gummy mass, highly soluble in ether and benzene, was obtained. It was taken up in ether and washed with 5% aqueous alkali; the product isolated from it was sublimed at 150-60°/0.1 mm. A colorless solid obtained from the sublimate after crystallisation from benzene melted at 156-58° and mixed m.p. with 8-hydroxycoumarin was found to be 154-56° (yield almost theoretical). (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 8 hrs.: C, 66.12; H, 3.4. Calc. for $C_9H_6O_3$: C, 66.67; H, 3.7%).

(ii) The allyl ether was heated in benzene as also in xylene following the same procedure as in the case of $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethyl allyl ether of 7-hydroxycoumarin. The reaction product was found to be the unchanged material (when heated in benzene), but 50% of the substance decomposed when heated in xylene.

4. *Thermal Decomposition of 7- $\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethylallyloxycoumarin*.—(i). The allyl ether (0.5 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene and refluxed on a water bath for 10 hrs. The solvent was then removed as completely as possible and the solid left was washed with 5% NaOH solution (aqueous), followed by water, and then crystallised repeatedly from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°), m.p. 77-78°; it did not depress the m.p. of the original substance. Aqueous washings on acidification and concentration left no residue.

(ii). The experiment was repeated in xylene. The residue left after removal of the solvent was repeatedly washed with 5% NaOH (aqueous) solution and then with water. The solid thus obtained was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°), which melted at 77-78° and did not depress the m.p. of the original substance. Aqueous alkali portion was acidified and concentrated. The solid recovered was purified and crystallised from dilute ethanol several times; it melted at 230-31° and showed no depression

in m.p. with an authentic sample of umbelliferone (about 5% of the allyl ether decomposed).

(iii). The above experiment (Claisen migration) was repeated at 175-85°/20 mm. The product is insoluble in benzene, ether and petroleum ether. On repeated crystallisation from dilute ethanol, the m.p. of the solid could be raised to 230-31° and the m.p. did not change when mixed with an authentic sample of umbelliferone (yield almost theoretical). (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 8 hrs.: C, 66.40; H, 3.78. Calc. for $C_9H_6O_3$: C, 66.67; H, 3.70%).

(iv). The above experiment was repeated under high vacuum (200-210°/01mm). Umbelliferone was recovered in about 90% of the theoretical yield.

*Isolation of Phenolic Coumarins and Isoprene (as its Maleic Anhydride Adduct)
from $\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethyl Allyl Ethers of Coumarins from Thermal Decomposition
Products during the Claisen Rearrangement*

$\gamma\gamma$ -Dimethyl allyl ether of umbelliferone (0.5 g.) and maleic anhydride (0.2 g.) were dissolved in dry xylene (10 ml) and heated in a sealed tube at 210° in a metal bath for 20 hrs. The products were cooled; the solid (A) separating was filtered, and the filtrate (B) was kept. Solid (A), crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 232°, was found to be identical with umbelliferone. The identity was established from its elementary analysis, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of umbelliferone. (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 8 hrs.: C, 66.67; H, 3.86. Calc. for $C_9H_6O_3$: C, 66.67; H, 3.70%).

Isolation of Isoprene-maleic Anhydride Adduct from the Filtrate (B).—The filtrate (B) was diluted with ether (25 ml) and extracted with sodium carbonate solution (3.15ml) and then hydrochloric acid (pH 5.5-6.0). The ether layer was washed with a little water, dried, and concentrated. The solid separating was crystallised from benzene in colorless flakes, m.p. 148-50°. It did not show any depression in m.p. when admixed with a synthetic sample of maleic anhydride adduct of isoprene. (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 10 hrs.: C, 58.38; H, 6.40. Calc. for $C_9H_{12}O_4$: C, 58.69; H, 6.52%).

Thermal decomposition of $\gamma\gamma$ -dimethyl allyl ether of 5-hydroxy-, 6-hydroxy-, and 8-hydroxy-coumarins was carried out following the same procedure described above in presence of maleic anhydride and the maleic anhydride adduct of isoprene was isolated in each case along with the corresponding phenolic coumarins.

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Errata

Page	Line	Read	For
541	Fig. 2	3.5 and 4.5 as log ϵ data for Curve II	
543	2	150 ml	50 ml
544	12	(log ϵ , 4.33, 3.84 & 3.80)	(log ϵ , 433, 384, 380)
	16	0.02 g.	0.2 g.
	20	-6 methoxy- coumurin	-6 methoxy- comarin
586	Figs 2 and 3	Read the legends interchanged	
705	Table II, last column, line 3	Zn (OH) ₂	Zn(OH ₂) ₂
721	Fig ⁵	"and Ionac A-300" before 'membrane'	